

Modelling of superconducting cable systems for marine applications in Ireland (SuperMarineOne)

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Review of Technology, Applications and Data; Numerical Modelling and Analysis of Cables in Operation and Installation

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Executive Summary:

The SuperMarineOne project focuses on numerical modelling and analysis of superconducting cables in operation and installation. Firstly, an overview of the current developments in superconducting cables was presented and issues with subsea cables that will affect submarine applications of superconducting cables are discussed and compared. Potential marine applications of superconducting cables in Ireland such as existing and proposed interconnectors and offshore wind farms were reviewed and analysed. A new design methodology for high temperature superconducting (HTS) cables to be used in marine applications is proposed. In addition, detail non-linear finite element models are developed to calculate the axial and bending stiffnesses of conventional HTS cables which have not been appropriately reported in public literature. From the conclusion that conventional HTS cables are not suitable for dynamic marine application, a novel structural concept for HTS cables is presented that enables such applications of the technology. Finally, the suitability of cable laying and

reel-lay vessels to install the HTS cable is reviewed and the effect of wave and current directions, wave peak periods and water depth during the installation process is investigated.

The studies carried out in the project find out that:

- (i) Currently, three HTS materials have been demonstrated worldwide for SC cable applications i.e. BSCCO, YBCO and MgB₂. Although there are several deployed and ongoing demonstration superconducting cable projects worldwide, no clear direction of which superconducting material is preferred for power cable applications.
- (ii) There are potential marine applications of superconducting technology in Ireland for adequate infrastructure and technology for offshore transmission and interconnectors in order to deploy large-scale electricity. Besides, there is huge potential for introducing superconducting technology for export cables and collectors in offshore wind farms to exploit the offshore wind potential of 34.8 GW – 39 GW in Ireland. Coupling with other energy sectors by the concepts of offshore wind – hydrogen production hubs being developed by the H-Wind project ⁽¹⁾ is another solution to increase the applications of superconducting technology.
- (iii) The free-hanging configuration is more suitable than the lazy-wave configuration for HTS cable applications at 100 m water depths. Even though the lazy wave configuration minimized the top tension on the cable, the addition of buoyant modulus introduced excessive axial compression that led to cable buckling in both designs. This occurs because the HTS cable is light in comparison to its external diameter and consequently its water displacement.
- (iv) According to the methodology proposed in the project, conventional HTS cable designs used in terrestrial applications are not suitable for dynamic marine applications. In order to allow HTS cables to be deployed in the marine environment an external armour structure to support the marine loads is required.
- (v) The novel structural concept for HTS cables specific for marine applications satisfies all design criteria in the extreme operation and installation conditions evaluated. This could enable further investigations and deployment of HTS technology in a number of marine applications.
- (vi) By comparing cable laying and reel-lay vessels, the latter is considered more suitable to install the HTS cable proposed. However, some cable laying vessels may be able to install the HTS cable. Having two different types of vessels available for installations could be another advantage.
- (vii) From an installation perspective, the critical environmental load direction for cable installation is caused by transversal waves (90° direction). However, this environmental load direction showed to only induce significant stresses to the HTS cable in a limited range of wave peak periods near the vessel's natural frequency of vibration in roll. The results also show that the pipe releasing ramp support is responsible for inducing significant bending moments to the HTS cable during installation.

¹ <https://www.marei.ie/project/h-wind/>

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List of Abbreviations

A_c	Carcass area	L_p	Pitch length
AC	Alternating Current	LW	Lazy wave
A_t	Cross-Section area of tendon	MBR	Minimum bending radius
$A_{t,cap}$	HTS tape current capacity	MWL	Mean water level
BC	Boundary conditions	n_l	Number of HTS layers
b_t	Tensile tendon width	n_t	Number of tensile tendons
b_{tape}	HTS tape width	PA-11	Polyamide-11
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide	P_{out}	Power output
DC	Direct current	PPLP	Polypropylene laminated paper
E	Modulus of elasticity	PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
EA	Axial stiffness	R	Mean layer radius
EI	Bending stiffness	RAO	Response amplitude operator
f_f	Filling factor	T_c	Critical Temperature
FH	Free hanging	TDP	Touch down point
GI	Torsional stiffness	Th	Carcass strip thickness
G_i	Shear modulus for the material in the i-th layer	T_p	Wave peak period
H_c	Carcass layer thickness	t_t	Tensile tendon thickness
H_s	Significant wave height	ν_a	Poisson ratio
HTS	High temperature superconducting	V_{out}	HTS cable voltage output
HVDC	High voltage direct current	WD	Water depth
I_2	Second moment of area of a tendon cross-section	α_c	Carcass laying angle
I_i	Second moment of area for a plastic layer cross-section	α_t	Tensile tendon laying angle
J	Torsional inertia of a tendon cross-section	α_{tape}	HTS tape laying angle
L_h	Horizontal length	θ	Carcass centre curvature angle
LN ₂	Liquid nitrogen		

1 Introduction

Superconducting transmission lines have a tremendous size advantage and lower total electrical losses for high-capacity transmission compared to solutions based on standard conductors. This leads to a minimized environmental impact and enables an overall more sustainable transmission of electric energy (Thomas et al., 2016). Furthermore, access to remote renewable energy sources with a high-capacity transmission is rendered possible with superior efficiency. That can also be translated into further decreases (or reductions) of CO₂ emissions in a global energy mix that is still primarily based on fossils (Thomas et al., 2016).

Likewise, conventional submarine power cables have for many years played a significant role in the transfer of energy on a worldwide scale. The applications include interconnection of autonomous power transmission grids to meet the needs of consumption during periods of high demand, to transfer electricity produced from offshore wind farms, to provide electricity to offshore oil and gas production platforms (in an effort to optimise the onboard space and reduce maintenance costs), and to perform electric heating to submarine pipelines in order to prevent wax and hydrate deposits (Ventikos and Stavrou, 2013).

Despite various major advantages of superconducting cable systems and promising applications in offshore projects, the behaviour, survival and serviceability of superconducting cable systems under marine environment have not been well studied nor publicly reported. Currently, superconducting cables have mostly being deployed in terrestrial applications, where the loads applied to the cables during installation and operation are minimized and controlled. Therefore, most of the superconducting cable studies focused on investigating the thermal/pressure losses (Hamabe et al., 2012; Shabagin et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2020) and overall performances of cables (Maguire et al., 2009; Soika, Garcia and Nogales, 2011).

In this context, the SuperMarineOne project aims to facilitate the development of superconducting cable systems in marine applications by investigating their survival and serviceability during dynamic operation and installation. The series of studies carried out are especially useful at preliminary design stages where the global loads acting on the cable are unknown and necessary for detailed local analysis and design of superconducting cables. Thus, in this project, an overview of the current developments in superconducting cables worldwide was presented and issues with subsea cables that will affect submarine applications of superconducting cables were discussed and compared. Potential marine applications of superconducting cables in Ireland such as existing and proposed interconnectors and offshore wind farms were reviewed and analysed. A new design methodology for HTS cables to be used in marine applications has been proposed. In addition, detail non-linear finite element models have been developed to calculate the axial and bending stiffnesses of conventional HTS cables which have not been appropriately reported in public literature. From the conclusion that conventional HTS cables are not suitable for dynamic marine application, a novel structural HTS cable concept was presented that enable such applications of the technology. Finally, the suitability of cable laying and reel-lay vessels to install the HTS cable was reviewed and the effect of wave and current directions, wave peak periods and water depth during the installation process were discussed.

2 Review of Technology, Applications and Data

This aimed to review superconducting cable technology and materials for submarine cable applications. An overview of the current developments in superconducting cables was presented. From a market perspective, the work package investigated potential marine applications of superconducting cables in Ireland such as existing and proposed interconnectors and offshore wind farms. It also presented potential issues with subsea cables and data on water depth, seabed stability, and ocean current and wave of Ireland's seas in order to support the future work packages in modelling operation and installation of superconducting cables in marine environments. They are also useful for ones who are/will be developing, designing, installing or operating marine superconducting cables and collectors.

2.1 Superconducting technology

Currently, three high temperature superconducting (HTS) materials have been demonstrated worldwide for superconducting cable applications i.e. BSCCO, YBCO and MgB₂. Both BSCCO and YBCO can operate at 77K (-196 °C) allowing a simplified design and, most importantly, the utilization of liquid nitrogen (LN₂) which is widely used in industrial applications, is inexpensive and available in most countries worldwide. On the other hand, the most recent technology, based on MgB₂ superconductors, needs to operate at much lower temperatures i.e. 15 to 30 K (-258 to -243 °C). Although there are additional costs from the increased cooling system requirements, they are compensated by the very low costs of MgB₂ wires, which makes power cables based on MgB₂ wires extremely attractive in an economic perspective. **Table 2-1** shows the common nomenclatures and critical temperatures (T_c) of these superconducting materials. The T_c refers to a certain material-specific temperature, when cooled below it, its thermodynamic properties reach the superconducting state.

Table 2-1: Common SC materials nicknames and critical temperatures (T_c).

Material	Common nomenclatures	T_c (K)
Bi ₂ Sr ₂ Ca ₂ Cu ₃ O ₁₀	BSCCO-2223; Bi-2223	110
Bi ₂ Sr ₂ CaCu ₂ O ₈	BSCCO-2212; Bi-2212	80 - 90
YBa ₂ Cu ₃ O ₇	YBCO; YBCO123; Y-123	92
MgB ₂	-	39

In order to evaluate the commercial development of HTS power cables, demonstration HTS cable projects were reviewed. **Figure 2-1** illustrates some of the demonstration HTS cable projects worldwide making a distinction between alternate current (AC) and direct current (DC) applications. In addition, the location, technical specifications and industry partners involved are mentioned for each project (Lee *et al.*, 2018). Although there are several deployed and ongoing demonstration SC cable projects worldwide, no clear direction of which superconducting material is preferred for power cable applications was found. Due to recent improvements in YBCO-based HTS cables performance, their lower costs in comparison to BSCCO technology, and their intrinsic fault current limiter capability, YBCO seems to have advantages over BSCCO wires in HTS cable applications. On the other hand, MgB₂-based superconducting cables have demonstrated significantly lower costs which are likely to boost the development of MgB₂ technology in the future. However, as far as the authors are concerned, currently, there is no ongoing demonstration project investigating marine/subsea applications of superconducting cables.

Figure 2-1: HTS power cable projects worldwide (Lee, et al., 2018).

2.2 Potential marine applications of superconducting cables in Ireland

The large-scale deployment of renewable energy sources adds new challenges to the electricity grid due to their variable and intermittent nature of energy production. In other words, the fluctuation of energy production over time and the possible mismatch between production and demand bring uncertainty regarding the resource requirements for maintaining power balance on the electricity grid. One possible solution to this problem is to increase the number of grid interconnections. In this context, **Figure 2-2** illustrates the existing and proposed electrical interconnectors for the whole island of Ireland. In addition, a summary of their capacities and project timeframes are presented in **Table 2-2**. Currently, Ireland has a total electricity interconnection capacity of 1GW, with a strong likelihood that the Celtic Interconnector project will go ahead, adding 700 MW capacity between Ireland and France (Pereira, et al., 2020). It is worth noticing that this study is taking an all-island and marine perspective and, therefore, the North-South interconnector is not described in the report.

Table 2-2: Present and future electrical interconnectors capacity of the isle of Ireland (Pereira, et al., 2020).

Interconnectors	Power capacity	Commissioned/Expected
Moyle	500MW	2001
East West	500MW	2012
Greenlink	500MW	2023
Celtic	700MW	2026

Figure 2-2: Existing and proposed electrical interconnectors in the island of Ireland (Pereira, et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the National Offshore Renewable Energy Development Plan (OREDPP) (DCCAE, 2014) indicates that the total amount of offshore wind farm development is between 34.8 GW and 39 GW without likely significant adverse effects on the environment. Moreover, a target of 70% electricity from renewables by 2030 was set in the recent Climate Action Plan (Government of Ireland, 2019). With improvements in technology and reductions in cost, offshore wind is at a new point of departure in Ireland.

In this regard, the combination of Ireland's low current interconnection capacity, huge offshore renewable energy resources, and limited internal electricity markets, create an attractive scenario for possible applications of superconducting technology in Ireland. As superconducting cables enable high current transmission, they obviate high voltage direct current (HVDC) platforms and facilitate higher power capacity transmission. Thus, their potential applications will likely fall in the range of large diameter power export cables (shown in **Figure 2-3**) or interconnectors.

Figure 2-3: Comparison of offshore wind farm collector topologies using conventional HVDC cable (upper) and superconducting cables (lower) (SuperNode, 2020).

2.3 Irish metocean data

Figure 2-4 shows the water depth around the island of Ireland. The Irish Sea is principally shallow to transitional water depths, with some areas reaching deep water closer to the territorial boundary with the UK. The water depth in Ireland increases dramatically along the south and west coast of Ireland, reaching 80m within 20 – 80km from shore, and 5 – 40km from shore respectively (Chester, et al., 2018).

Wave conditions directly relate and govern the access to the site for cable laying, and to the survivability of cables during laying processes. In accordance with Health and Safety factors, most offshore activities are restricted to the conditions that they can work within. These weather limits vary depending on the activities that are being conducted, and the equipment and/or vessels that are being used. Offshore operations require stringent logistical planning to identify viable weather windows in order to conduct activities (Chester, et al., 2018).

Mean annual significant wave heights (Hs) and periods around the coast of Ireland are presented in Figure 2-5 and Figure 2-6, respectively. The Northeast Atlantic has one of the greatest wave climates in the world, generated by surface winds that produce large swells which can propagate across the Atlantic to first reach landfall on the western coast of Ireland. The west coast witnesses an average of 2.0m Hs in the summer and 4.0m Hs during the winter (Chester, et al., 2018).

Figure 2-4: Map of Ireland bathymetry [Source: 4Coffshore] (Chester, et al., 2018).

Mean Annual Significant Wave

— Designated_Maritime_Boundary_Continental_Shelf

□ Navy_12_Nautical_Mile

Mean_Annual_Distribution_of_Wave_Height__m_

Figure 2-5: Mean annual significant wave height (m) around the coast of Ireland (Chester, et al., 2018).

Mean Annual Wave Period

- Designated_Maritime_Boundary_Continental_Shelf
- Navy_12_Nautical_Mile

Mean_Annual_Distribution_of_Wave_Period__Sec_

- 4.75
- 5
- 5.25
- 5.5
- 5.75
- 6
- 6.25
- 6.5
- 6.75
- 7
- 7.25
- 7.5
- 7.75
- 8
- 8.25
- 8.5
- 8.75
- 9

Figure 2-6: Mean annual period (s) of wave around the coast of Ireland (Chester, et al., 2018).

2.4 Issues with subsea cables

As subsea cable systems are subjected to various loads including functional, environmental or accidental loads, and can be damaged in several ways, it is important to first identify the site-physical dependences of each subsea cable project. For both cable designing and laying companies, awareness of possible problems of subsea cables and their causes is important. From understanding these site-dependence and possible issues, suitable measures can be properly proposed, for modelling and practical implementation. Thus, site-physical dependences of subsea cable projects presented in the literature including seabed conditions, tides and currents, and waves have been reviewed. Possible problems of subsea cables and their causes include cable exposure (due to scour, sand wave mitigation, and sediment depletion), suspended cables, and reduction of cable cooling (for example due to sediment accretion). Other possible issues including damages by heavy ships' anchors and human activities (such as bottom trawl fishing), faulty installation, and damages by natural hazards, and environmental impact of the cable installation process (such as sediment transport, intertidal habitats, and shipping and navigation) and possible mitigation measure are also reviewed. These aim to assist the readers in further understand possible issues and propose suitable measures, for modelling and practical implementation stages.

3 Cable in Operation: Numerical Modelling and Analysis

In this section, the survival and serviceability of superconducting cable systems operating in marine applications are investigated. In this regard, a new design methodology for HTS cables to be used in marine applications has been proposed. This new methodology was based on the existing regulatory framework used for flexible pipes, most notably, the API 17B (API 17B, 2002) and API 17J (API 17J, 2008) on design recommendations for flexible pipes, and the DNVGL-ST-F101 standard for submarine pipeline systems (DNVGL, 2017). Thus, according to the proposed methodology, the design of HTS cable systems for marine applications should follow the design steps described in the flow chart illustrated in **Figure 3-1**.

Figure 3-1: Flow chart to describe the proposed design steps for the design of offshore HTS cable systems

3.1 Conventional HTS cables

3.1.1 Cross-Section design of conventional HTS cables

The importance of considering the effect of the operating cryogenic temperatures on the material selection stage and during the calculation of the HTS cable mechanical properties for the design of the HTS cable has been investigated. Furthermore, non-linear finite element models have been developed to calculate the axial and bending stiffnesses of conventional HTS cables which have not been appropriately reported in public literature. Conventional HTS cables refer to cable designs originally used in terrestrial applications.

In order to demonstrate the methodology, two HTS cable designs to operate as dynamic export cables for offshore wind farms are proposed and their survival and serviceability is investigated through static and dynamic global analyses. **Figure 3-2** describes the cable architecture used as a reference where: (1) is the copper core; (2) are the HTS tapes; (3) is the voltage insulation or dielectric; (4) is the copper shielding; (5) is the liquid nitrogen (LN₂) inlet; (6) is the inner cryostat; and (7) is the outer cryostat which is separated from the inner cryostat by a vacuum layer.

Figure 3-2: HTS cable architecture with copper core. Adapted from (Maguire *et al.*, 2009).

The first design step is to determine the copper core diameter to accommodate enough HTS tapes to transport the desired power output (P_{out}). In this regard, **Eq. 1** is proposed to calculate the copper core diameter required to support enough HTS tapes to transport the desired power output in HTS cables where D_{cc} is the copper core diameter, V_{out} is the HTS cable voltage output, $A_{t, cap}$ is the HTS tape current capacity, b_{tape} is the HTS tape width, α_{tape} is the HTS tape laying angle, n_l is the number of HTS layers, and f_f is the filling factor of the HTS layers.

$$D_{cc} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{P_{out}}{V_{out} A_{t, cap}} \frac{b_{tape}}{n_l \cos(\alpha_{tape}) f_f} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Assuming a P_{out} of 2 GW, two copper core diameters were achieved with 30 mm and 60 mm. Having attained the copper core diameter, the other layers of the HTS cable were designed around its dimension (see **Figure 3-2**). The subsequent layers of HTS tapes are added based on a YBCO tape with a thickness of 0.4 mm (SuperPower, 2021). The dielectric was assumed to have a thickness of 15 mm based on the discussions presented in (Bruzek *et al.*, 2015; Kim *et al.*, 2016; Peng *et al.*, 2019). The copper shielding was set having a thickness of 3 mm according to common design specifications (Stemmler *et al.*, 2013). Finally, in order to avoid detailed thermal analysis of the HTS cable, an arbitrary LN₂ and vacuum thicknesses of 30 mm each was selected using conservative assumptions based on the HVDC HTS cable design presented in (Bruzek *et al.*, 2015) and industry consultation (Supernode, 2021). Thus, the internal arrangement of the HTS cable under steady-state operation (filled with LN₂) and the respective weight of each layer are described in **Table 3-1**.

Table 3-1: Detailed description of both proposed HTS cable designs including diameter and weight estimation by layer. The numbers in parenthesis are the reference numbers illustrated in **Figure 3-2**.

Layer (ref.)	Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Design 1		Design 2	
			Out. Diam. D1 (mm)	Weight D1 (kg/m)	Out. Diam. D2 (mm)	Weight D2 (kg/m)
Copper core (1)	Copper	8900	30	6.3	60	25.2
HTS tapes (2)	HTS	9000	33.2	1.3	61.6	1.3
Dielectric (3)	PPLP	9200	63.2	2	91.6	3.3
Cu shielding (4)	Copper	8900	69.2	5.5	97.6	7.9
LN ₂ return (5)	LN ₂	812	129.2	7.6	157.6	9.8
Inner cryostat (6)	Stainless Steel	8000	144.8	8.3	173.2	10.0
Outer cryostat (7)	Stainless Steel	8000	204.8	12.1	233.2	13.8
Total				43.1		71.3

3.1.2 Mechanical properties of conventional HTS cables

To carry out the global analysis and evaluate the survival and serviceability of HTS cable in the marine environment, the mechanical properties of the cable must be known first, most notably, its axial and bending stiffnesses, maximum allowable tension, and minimum bending radius (MBR). As described in Section 3.1.1, HTS cables have a complex architecture in order to maintain the operating cryogenic temperatures that allow superconductivity. In their composition, the inner components of the HTS cable (i.e. copper core, HTS tapes, dielectric and copper shielding) are separated from the inner and outer cryostats by an LN₂ layer. For that reason, it is assumed that the mechanical properties of the HTS cable are governed by the inner and outer cryostat structures. Thus, numerical model models were developed using finite element analysis to obtain the mechanical characteristics of the designed double cryostat walls for the proposed HTS cable designs.

Figure 3-3: 10-pitch long double cryostat model used for tension stiffness analysis.

The capabilities and suitability of available software were reviewed and Abaqus standard/explicit 6.14 was chosen to carry out the simulations. Because the ratio between thickness and global size of the model is much lower than 1/10, the corrugated pipe is modelled using 3D S4R thin-walled shell elements. Even though in practical applications the cryostat has helical corrugation, as demonstrated in (Srivastava, Buitrago and Slocum, 2011), the use of axisymmetric models to analyse the cryostat under axial and bending loads has no impact on the results but significantly improves the modelling process and time efficiency during calculations. Therefore, both the inner and outer cryostat walls for

all tests were modelled with axisymmetric corrugation. **Figure 3-3** illustrates a 10-pitch long double cryostat model used for tension stiffness analysis.

Finally, the non-linear axial and bending stiffnesses of the HTS cable are presented in **Figure 3-4** and **Figure 3-5**, respectively. The maximum allowable tension and MBR are set to avoid any plastic deformation in the cryostat structures. In this regard, the maximum allowable tension for Design 1 and Design 2 are respectively 57 kN and 60 kN and both occur at approximately 0.033 strain. The MBR likewise, is 5 m for Design 1 and 5.2 m for Design 2 which corresponds to the curvature where plastic deformation starts to happen. Although both designs possess similar MBR's, the bending stiffness of Design 2 is 40% higher than Design 1 at 0.2 curvature. It is also worth noting that all the loads in the global analysis are applied within the cable plane, therefore, the torsional stiffness has no impact in the case studies investigated in this project.

Figure 3-4: Axial stiffness of both HTS cable designs proposed in this project. The dashed line represents the maximum allowable tension in which plastic deformation starts.

Figure 3-5: Bending stiffness of both HTS cable designs proposed in this project. The dashed lines represent the minimum bending radius in which plastic deformation starts in each design.

3.1.3 System configuration design of conventional HTS cables

In order to implement the proposed methodology, the survival and serviceability of two HTS cable systems are evaluated in free hanging and lazy wave configurations at a hypothetical site with a WD of 100 m. The geometric parameters used to characterize the free hanging and lazy wave configurations are the water depth (WD), horizontal length (L_h) and cable length, whereas the geometric parameters exclusively applied to the lazy wave configuration are the buoyant section length, buoyant section start and buoyant section end (see **Figure 3-6**). **Table 3-2** describes these geometric parameters. The parameters used were set based on other flexible riser systems available in the literature (Keprate, 2014; Du Kim *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 3-6: Cable parameters description for free hanging (a) and lazy wave (b) system configuration design.

Table 3-2: Geometric parameters used to characterize the system configuration designs.

Parameter	Configuration ¹	Case study
Water depth, WD	FH and LW	100 m
Horizontal length, L_h	FH and LW	120 m
HTS cable length	FH and LW	180 m
Buoyant section length	LW	40 m
Buoyant section start	LW	40 m
Buoyant section end	LW	80 m

¹ FH = free hanging configuration; LW = lazy wave configuration.

Furthermore, **Table 3-3** describes the mechanical properties and geometric characteristics of both HTS cable designs proposed. The equivalent internal diameter was calculated using an area-equivalent approach which refers to the diameter with the same area as the cable cross-section conveying LN_2 . The MBR and maximum allowable tension are obtained from the local analyses described in Section 3.1.2. The non-linear axial and bending stiffnesses are given in **Figure 3-4** and **Figure 3-5** respectively whereas the torsion stiffness was assumed to be constant and equals to $80 \text{ kN.m}^2/\text{rad}$ based on (Buitrago *et al.*, 2010; Kothari, Niu and Srivastava, 2019). The weight in the air (Empty) of the HTS cable is calculated by subtracting the weight related to the LN_2 from the overall weight of the HTS cable. The content density refers to the density of LN_2 . Finally, the buoyant section details for each case are presented in **Table 3-4**.

Table 3-3: Cable description for both proposed HTS cable designs.

Parameters	Design 1	Design 2	Units
Equivalent internal diameter	109.0	123.7	mm
Outer diameter	204.8	233.2	mm
Minimum bending radius, MBR	5.0	5.2	m
Allowable tension	57	60	kN
Axial stiffness	Figure 3-4	Figure 3-4	MN
Bending stiffness	Figure 3-5	Figure 3-5	kN.m ²
Torsion stiffness	80	80	kN.m ² /rad
Weight in air, Empty	36	62	kg/m
Content density	812	812	kg/m ³

Table 3-4: Buoyant section description for both proposed HTS cable designs.

Parameter	Design 1	Design 2
Buoyant section outer diameter	280 mm	390 mm
Buoyant section weight in air, Empty	47 kg/m	92 kg/m
Buoyant material density	400 kg/m ³	400 kg/m ³

Having attained the mechanical properties of the cable including the buoyant section, the system configuration design is calculated through static analysis using Abaqus software. Figure 3-7 illustrates the geometry, curvature, effective tension, and axial (true wall) tension of both HTS cables in lazy wave and free hanging configurations under static loads.

Figure 3-7: Static geometry, curvature, effective tension and axial (true wall) tension of both HTS cable designs in free hanging (FH) and lazy wave (LW) configurations. D1 = Design 1; D2 = Design 2.

With the results of the static analysis, the failure modes (i.e. excessive tension, excessive compression and overbending) are checked against design criteria and the results are presented in **Table 3-5**. To satisfy the design criteria for excessive tension the tension in the cable needs to be lower than 0.67 of the tension that causes plastic deformation into the cryostat, the compression needs to be lower than 0.67 the compression force that causes buckling of the cryostats whereas the MBR needs to be not less than 1.5 times the MBR that causes plastic deformation into the cryostats.

Table 3-5: Failure mode check against design criteria of both conventional HTS cable designs proposed under static loads.

Configuration	Substation offset	Design 1			Design 2		
		Tension Failure	Compression Failure	Overbending	Tension Failure	Compression Failure	Overbending
Free hanging	Near	0.20	0.42	4.0	0.51	0.46	3.8
	Nominal	0.22	0.39	8.7	0.61	0.40	8.3
	Far	0.27	0.37	14.3	0.70	0.31	13.6
Lazy wave	Nominal	0.16	0.73	4.0	0.43	1.5	3.8

Thus, it was concluded that the free-hanging configuration is more suitable than the lazy-wave configuration for HTS cable applications at 100 m water depths. Even though the lazy wave configuration minimized the top tension on the cable, the addition of buoyant modulus introduced excessive axial compression that led to cable buckling in both designs. This occurred because the HTS cable is light in comparison to its external diameter and consequently its water displacement.

3.1.4 Dynamic analysis of conventional HTS cables

Because significant compression forces were found in lazy wave configuration, the dynamic analysis was carried out only for the free hanging configuration. The dynamic analyses were performed according to the dynamic load case matrix described in **Table 3-6** for normal (or intact) operation under functional and environmental load cases. Regarding the load case matrix, in the substation offset, intact refers to the mooring system condition. The near case has the environment loads and substation offset oriented towards the cable seabed connection whereas the far case is oriented away from the cable seabed connection. Both near and far cases are oriented along the plane of the HTS cable and the substation offsets are considered to be 10% of the designed water depth (Keprate, 2014).

Table 3-6: Dynamic load case matrix for normal (intact) operation under functional and environmental loads.

Parameter	Nominal	Nominal	Near	Far
Water depth ¹	MWL	MWL	MWL	MWL
Internal pressure	Operating	Operating	Operating	Operating
Substation offset	Nominal intact	Nominal intact	Near intact	Far intact
Current	Near, 10-year	Far, 10-year	Near, 10-year	Far, 10-year
Irregular wave height	Near, 100-year	Far, 100-year	Near, 100-year	Far, 100-year
Irregular wave Period	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean

¹ MWL = Mean water level.

For dynamic analysis of flexible pipes, a combination of 10-year current and 100-year wave has to be considered (API 17B, 2002). Due to the lack of specific information on a deployment location, this set of information was estimated based on a site with characteristics similar to the case studies analysed in this report, namely, the Forties Oil Field at the North Sea. The Forties Oil Field is located at 177 km

offshore from Aberdeen within the UK at a water depth of 106 m (Offshore Technology, 2020). In this context, the 10-year current (Karunakaran and Baarholm, 2013) and 100-year sea state (Husain, 2006) used in the dynamic analysis are given in **Table 3-7**. The sea state is modelled by using irregular waves based on the JONSWAP wave spectrum.

Table 3-7: Dynamic loads applied to the HTS cable based on extreme sea state data for a typical Northern Sea location.

Parameters	Value	Units
10-year current	0.5	m/s
100-year wave height	12	m
100-year wave period	11.5	s
Irregular wave spectrum	JONSWAP	

The system configuration design was investigated regarding its curvature and effective tension for both proposed HTS cable designs under dynamic loads. This provides the necessary input for evaluating the HTS cable failure modes when subjected to environmental loads. In addition, the influence of the current/wave direction and cable design in the curvature and effective tension of the HTS cable is discussed. In this section, only relevant data to support the discussions are presented in the form of figures. **Figure 3-8** illustrates the maximum curvature and effective tension along the HTS cable highlighting the different responses of each HTS cable design. With this information, their failure modes can be checked. **Table 3-8** presents the failure modes checked against the design criteria of both HTS cable designs in free hanging configuration. Overall, both designs failed due to over-bending when subjected to dynamic loads. In addition, Design 2 also failed due to over tension.

Figure 3-8: Maximum curvature (left) and minimum/maximum effective tension (right) along the cable length for both HTS cable designs. First index: Nom/Near/Far = floating substation offset; Second index: Near/Far = direction of current and wave.

Both cable designs were evaluated under dynamic loads and free hanging configuration. In the dynamic analysis, Design 1, which has a smaller and lighter core, did not fail due to over tension but experienced excessive curvature and displacements due to the lack of weight and tension in the cable. On the other hand, Design 2, due to its larger and heavier core, even though it demonstrated minimized curvatures and displacement under dynamic loads, failed due to over tension. Thus, according to the proposed methodology, conventional onshore HTS cable designs are not suitable for dynamic marine applications. In order to allow HTS cables to be deployed in the marine environment an external armour structure to support the dynamic marine loads is required.

Table 3-8: Failure modes for the load case matrix for both conventional HTS cable designs proposed under dynamic loads.

Substation offset	Wave and Current direction	Design 1			Design 2		
		Tension Failure	Compression Failure	Overbending	Tension Failure	Compression Failure	Overbending
Nominal	Near	0.28	0.03	0.31	0.66	0.05	0.59
Nominal	Far	0.49	0.03	0.71	0.85	-	1.22
Near	Near	0.28	0.03	0.52	0.57	-	0.59
Far	Far	0.62	0.08	0.71	1.03	-	1.65

3.2 Novel structural concept for HTS cables with external armour

3.2.1 Cross-section design of the novel structural concept for HTS cables

The offshore HTS cable concept and unbonded flexible pipes are similar in their goal and general operating conditions. In this context, the design of the armouring structures required for marine applications of HTS cables was based on the architecture of unbonded flexible pipes. A typical architecture of a flexible pipe is composed of a series of layers, each one of them having very specific roles. **Figure 3-9** shows an example of a common internal architecture of a flexible pipe. The carcass has the objective of supporting the fluid barrier and preventing collapse from external pressure or crushing loads. The pressure sheath is a polymer layer made of chemically resistant material to convey the operating fluid. The pressure armour aims to resist internal pressure loads. The tensile armour intends to support primarily axial tension and torsion moments, but they also contribute on a smaller scale to the bending moments and internal pressure. The anti-friction layers, or also called anti-wear layers, are thin polymer layers introduced between any adjacent metallic layers in order to avoid metal-to-metal contact preventing friction and wear. Finally, the outer sheath is the external barrier made of polymer with the goal of preventing mechanical damage and seawater intrusion (Yun, Jang and Du Kim, 2020).

Figure 3-9: Armour structure composition of flexible pipes. Adapted from (Yun, Jang and Du Kim, 2020).

Based on the Design 2 described in **Table 3-1** and the cross-section architecture of unbonded flexible pipes, a new HTS cable concept specific for marine applications is proposed in this project. Essentially, the proposed design substitutes the outer cryostat for the carcass followed by the pressure sheath, antifriction tapes, tensile armour layers and the outer sheath. In this way, instead of the double cryostat wall having to support all the loads, the carcass will cope with the external pressure loads while the tensile armour layers will withstand the other loads imposed on the HTS cable. It is worth

noting that the pressure armour was not considered in the proposed design as the cable will not be subjected to significant internal pressure loads which is the role of this structural layer. In this way, the tensile tendons must withstand the low internal pressure loads that may appear in the case of a failure of the inner cryostat.

The design of the external armour structures, namely the carcass, pressure sheath, antifriction tapes, tensile armour layers and the outer sheath was carried out based on design recommendations for flexible pipes presented in (API 17B, 2002), the DNVGL-ST-F101 standard for submarine pipeline systems (DNVGL, 2017) and the handbook on design and operation of flexible pipes (MARINTEK, NTNU and 4Subsea, 2017). However, thorough consideration was given to the potential failure modes caused by the LN₂ operating at cryogenic temperatures into all layers of the new HTS cable concept.

In this context, **Table 3-9** presents detailed information on the HTS layers, carcass profile, tensile tendons, and plastic layers of the new HTS cable concept. The cable described in **Table 3-9** is the resulted design of several interactions of the design methodology described in **Figure 3-1**. Thus, **Table 3-10** describes the novel structural HTS cable cross-section including the outer diameter, materials used, material density, and weight estimation of each respective layer. The new HTS cable at steady-state operation (filled with LN₂) weights 99 kg/m, which is almost double its water displacement weight of 51 kg/m. On the other hand, when empty (i.e. installation condition), the weight of the cable is 89.2 kg/m which is 75% higher than its water displacement weight.

Table 3-9: Detailed information of external armour for the proposed HTS cable design.

Parameters	Value	Units
Carcass		
Carcass layer thickness, H_c	7.5	mm
Carcass strip thickness, th	1.5	mm
Carcass centre curvature angle, θ	60	degrees
Carcass laying angle, α_c	87.5	degrees
Carcass pitch length, L_p	27.8	mm
Carcass Area, A_c	136.2	mm ²
Tensile tendons		
Tensile tendon thickness, t_t	3	mm
Tensile tendon width, b_t	7.5	mm
Tensile tendon laying angle, α_t	35	degrees
Filling factor, f_f	0.95	
Number of tensile tendons (in), n_t	74	
Number of tensile tendons (out), n_t	77	
Tensile tendon pitch length (in), L_p	1.02	m
Tensile tendon pitch length (out), L_p	1.06	m
Plastic layers		
Pressure sheath thickness	5	mm
Anti-friction tape thickness	1.5	mm
Outer sheath thickness	5	mm

Table 3-10: Novel structural HTS cable cross-section design describing outer diameters, materials, and weight estimates.

Layer	Outer diam. (mm)	Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Weight (kg/m)
Copper core	60.0	Copper	8900	25.2
HTS tapes	61.6	HTS	9000	1.2
Dielectric	91.6	PPLP	9200	3.3
Cu shielding	97.6	Copper	8900	7.9
LN ₂ return	157.6	LN ₂	812	9.8
Inner cryostat	173.2	Stainless Steel (316L)	8000	10.0
Carcass	217.6	Stainless Steel (316L)	8000	1.1
Pressure sheath	227.6	PTFE	800	2.8
Inner tensile	233.6	Carbon steel	8000	16.5
Anti-friction	236.6	PA-11	800	0.9
Outer tensile	242.6	Carbon steel	8000	17.2
Outer sheath	252.6	PA-11	800	3.1
Total:				99

3.2.2 Mechanical properties of the novel structural concept for HTS cables

The mechanical properties of the HTS cable are dictated by the external armour structure which was based on flexible pipe designs. Thus, analytical models of the axial, bending and torsional stiffnesses of flexible pipes were used to estimate such stiffnesses of the HTS cable structure proposed in this report. Both the axial and torsional stiffnesses are governed by the tensile armour layers (MARINTEK, NTNU and 4Subsea, 2017). Therefore, the axial stiffness and torsional stiffnesses were estimated using respectively **Eq. 2** and **Eq. 3** where n_t is the number of tensile tendons in the layer, E is the modulus of elasticity, A_t is the cross-section area of the tendon, α_t is the laying angle of the tendon, ν_a is the poisson ratio and R is the mean radius of the armouring layer (MARINTEK, NTNU and 4Subsea, 2017). It is important to mention that both **Eq. 2** and **Eq. 3** assume that all layers remain in contact.

$$EA = n_t EA_t \cos \alpha_t (\cos^2 \alpha_t - \nu_a \sin^2 \alpha_t) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$GI = n_t EA_t R^2 \sin^2 \alpha_t \cos \alpha_t \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

On the other hand, analysis of bending stiffness of flexible pipes and consequently of the HTS cable is more complex than that of the axial and torsional stiffnesses. This is due to a hysteresis behaviour of nonbonded pipes that comes from an internal slip mechanism. For simplicity, hysteresis will not be considered in this report. Instead, a conservative linear analytical model proposed by (Ramos Jr and Pesce, 2004) is used to estimate the bending stiffness of the HTS cable. **Eq. 4** describes how the bending stiffness of the HTS cable is calculated which considers the contribution of all layers where p is the number of plastic layers, m is the number of helically armour layers, G_i is the shear modulus for the material of the i -th layer, I_i is the second moment of area for a plastic layer cross-section, J is the torsional inertia of a tendon cross-section, and I_2 is the second moment of area of a tendon cross-section with respect to transversal direction.

$$EI = \sum_{i=1}^p E_i I_i + \sum_{i=1}^m n_i \cos \alpha_i \left[G_i J_i + \frac{3}{2} (E_i I_{2,i} - G_i J_i) \cos^2 \alpha_i \right] \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The analytical model used for calculating the bending stiffness of the designed HTS cable works under the following assumptions (Ramos Jr and Pesce, 2004):

- (i) All layers present the same twist and elongation per unit of pipe length;
- (ii) There is no gap between adjacent layers;
- (iii) There is no contact between adjacent tendons in the same layer;
- (iv) All materials are homogeneous, isotropic and have linear elastic behaviour;
- (v) Pipe ovalisation is not considered; and
- (vi) Full-slip conditions between the tendons of armour layers and adjacent layers are assumed.

Thus, **Table 3-11** describes the mechanical properties and geometric characteristics of the novel HTS cable proposed. The maximum allowable tension, MBR and cable stiffness were calculated according to the established formulas described in detail in (MARINTEK, NTNU and 4Subsea, 2017), therefore, are not presented in this document.

Table 3-11: Novel HTS cable mechanical properties and geometric characteristics description.

Parameters	Value	Units
Equivalent internal diameter	124	mm
Outer diameter	253	mm
Minimum bending radius	2.6	m
Maximum allowable tension	369.0	kN
Axial stiffness	320.4	MN
Bending stiffness	18.2	kN.m ²
Torsion stiffness	1.2	MN.m ² /rad
Weight in air, Empty	89.2	kg/m
Content density	812	kg/m ³

3.2.3 Dynamic analysis of the novel structural concept for HTS cables

Following the proposed methodology, the novel structural concept for HTS cables under operational loads was analysed. The case study investigated the structure concept connecting a floating substation platform to the seabed in free hanging configuration at a water depth of 100 m (see free hanging configuration details in **Figure 3-6**). **Table 3-12** presents the critical loads and checks their respective failure modes against their design criteria. Furthermore, the substation offset, wave/current directions, and the cable region where the critical load are found is also outlined. Design criteria were based on the stress utilization of the respective structural layer according to the existing regulatory framework for flexible pipes presented in (API 17B, 2002; API 17J, 2008; MARINTEK, NTNU and 4Subsea, 2017). In order to satisfy the design criteria for collapse, tensile failure and compressive failure, the stress utilization of the layer needs to be less than 0.67 whereas for overbending the MBR during operation is required to be higher than 1.5 of the storage MBR. In this regard, the cross-section of the proposed cable structure concept satisfied all design criteria and, therefore, is found able to withstand all the operational loads according to the methodology proposed.

Table 3-12: Critical loads and failure modes check for operation.

Load (Failure mode)	substation offset and wave/current direction of maximum load	Maximum value (cable region)	Design criteria
External pressure (Collapse)	Same for all cases	1.17 MPa (TDP) ¹	0.22
Effective tension (Tensile failure)	Far	121 kN (Hang off)	0.16
Axial compression (Compression failure)	Near	30 kN (TDP) ¹	0.36
MBR² (Overbending)	Near	4.62 m (TDP) ¹	1.78

¹TDP = Touch Down Point

²MBR = Minimum Bending Radius

4 Cable Installation: Numerical Modelling and Analysis

4.1 Installation analysis methodology

After selecting an HTS cable design that satisfies all design criteria under static and dynamic operational loads, the feasibility of the proposed installation method must be checked. According to (API 17B, 2002), the installation load cases should account for all relevant functional and environmental loads as applicable to the installation method, vessel and environment. In this context, **Table 4-1** presents the installation load cases to evaluate the feasibility of the installation method proposed. These cases should also be performed for a number of loading directions, such as 0°, 45°, 90°, 135°, and 180° (API 17B, 2002).

Table 4-1: Installation load cases parameters.

Parameter	Installation load
Water depth	Mean water level
Internal pressure	Empty
Vessel offset ¹	10% water depth
Current	10-year
Irregular wave height	Vessel max. design wave
Irregular wave period	Range

¹ Vessel offset is in the same direction as the environmental loads.

The evaluation of the installation method in this project follows the methodology described in the flow chart illustrated in **Figure 4-1**. The first step is the selection of the vessel and understanding of the equipment onboard the vessel (which?) can handle the HTS cable without inducing overbending. For the dynamic analysis one of the most important information is the response amplitude operator (RAO) of the vessel. In this project, the RAO is calculated using the finite element software ANSYS/AQWA 2020 R1. In possession of the RAO data, the catenary curve is determined, and the environmental loads are specified based on the deployment location and the natural frequencies of vibration of the installation vessel to induce the most critical scenarios.

Thus, the dynamic analysis of cable installation is carried out by using the software PipeLay v2020.1.1 (Wood, 2021). From the results of the dynamic analysis, the failure modes of the HTS cable are checked against its design criteria. The top tension of the cable also needs to be smaller than the vessel's tensioner capacity. In case of all the criteria mentioned above are satisfied the installation method and vessel are considered suitable for the installation of the HTS cable in this report. It is worth mentioning that this project is considering only the HTS cable laying at the seabed after the HTS cable is already connected. According to the regulatory framework used for the installation of flexible pipes (API 17B, 2002), there are other analyses those needs to be assessed to fully validate the installation method proposed including the connection procedure of the cable to the seabed; and the crushing collapse under radial compression in the tensioner, and under torsional loads.

Figure 4-1: Installation design methodology flow chart.

4.2 Installation vessel

Due to the internal architecture, external diameter, and overall weight of the novel cable structure concept, it is not clear what type of vessel is better suited for its installation. In the current context, there are two types of vessels available in the market that can potentially be used for their installation i.e. cable laying vessels and reel-lay vessels. Thus, the suitability of cable laying and reel-lay vessels to install the proposed HTS cable must be investigated.

Table 4-2 presents and compares the main characteristics of two cable laying and two reel-lay vessels. From **Table 4-2**, overall, cable laying vessels present considerably lower MBR in their cable handling equipment than the MBR found on reel-lay vessels. This is because reel-lay vessels are designed to also install rigid pipes (in?) which MBR requirements are considerably higher than typical cables or flexible pipes. In addition, besides the inner carousel diameter, typically the MBRs of the pick-up arms on cable laying vessels are smaller than the carousel and must be taken into consideration.

Thus, the project focuses on reel-lay vessels for the installation of the proposed HTS cable. The higher MBR while handling the HTS cable and the controllable releasing top angle during installation minimize the stresses induced to the cable during installation and during cable handling by the vessel's equipment. However, the potential to use cable laying vessels to install HTS cables should not be discarded and should be investigated in a future study.

Table 4-2: Comparison between commercial cable laying and reel-lay vessels.

Vessel Name	Leonardo da Vinci	Nexans Aurora	Apache	Seven Oceans
Vessel Type	Cable Laying	Cable laying	Reel Laying	Reel Laying
Length	171 m	149.9	122.9 m	157.3 m
Breadth	34 m	31 m	23.3 m	28.4 m
Depth	-	12.8 m	8.7 m	12.5 m
Draught	8.5 m	8.3 m	5.6 m	7.5 m
Inner diameter of reel or carousel	6 m ¹	9.6 m ²	16.4 m	18 m
Top Tension	9810 kN	-	1530 kN	3925 kN

¹ Vessel contains two carrousel, and the carrousel pick up arm MBR is 3 m.

² Pick-up arm MBR not informed.

4.3 Vessel response amplitude operator

Vessel movements relative to the sea are among the main contributors to the loads induced to the HTS cable during installation. In order to understand these loads, the movements of the vessel due to the incidence of current and waves must be known, and are represented by the vessel’s RAO. RAOs are the transfer functions which translate the incident wave amplitude and period into vessel responses in all degrees of freedom (Wang *et al.*, 2020). Because RAO data is typically not publicly available due to proprietary reasons, in this report, an installation vessel with main dimensions and hull shape based on the reel-lay vessel Seven Oceans (Royal IHC, 2007) is modelled and its RAOs are calculated by using the software ANSYS/AQWA 2020 R1 v19. **Figure 4-2** illustrates the RAO curves for the installation vessel studied in this report for wave directions of 0°, 45°, 90°, 135°, and 180° whereas **Table 4-3** presents the vessel parameters and hydrostatic details. The wave frequency range was determined in order to capture the natural frequencies of vibrations in all degrees of freedom and to also include the wave periods of interest.

Figure 4-2: Installation vessel response amplitude operator (RAO) for incident wave directions of 0°, 45°, 90°, 135°, and 180°.

Table 4-3: Vessel parameter and hydrostatic details.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Overall length	157.3 m	Ship displacement	27,570 T
Breadth	28.4 m	Centre of gravity ¹	1.0 m
Depth	12.5 m	Metacentre height ¹	5.4 m
Draught	7.5 m	Centre of floatation ¹	-1.0 m

¹ Value taken from mean water level.

4.4 Submerged catenary curve

The dynamic analysis starts by calculating the static equilibrium of the cable, or in other words, the submerged catenary curve. In this report, the software PipeLay v2020.1.1 was used to calculate the static equilibrium of the HTS cable. Three models were developed at water depths of 50, 75, and 100 meters to account for the varying water depth during installation from the coast to the connection site. **Table 4-4** describes the parameters used to describe the static catenary curve estimated for each water depth.

Table 4-4: Parameters for static analysis

Parameters	WD - 100	WD - 75	WD - 50
HTS cable length	300 m	250 m	200 m
Horizontal length, L_h	225 m	188 m	151 m
Releasing top angle	70°	70°	70°
Seabed	Rigid	Rigid	Rigid

According to typical design recommendations for flexible pipes installation (API 17B, 2002), in the dynamic analysis, the vessel is offset to a position equivalent to 10% of the water depth in the same direction of the applied environmental loads from the initial position described in **Table 4-4**. **Figure 4-3** illustrates the change in the vessel offset according to the environmental loads' direction, in this case, 180°.

Figure 4-3: Vessel offset according to the environmental loads' direction, in this case 180°.

4.5 Environmental conditions

For the dynamic installation analysis, a weather window for safe installation must be selected. In this regard, the maximum installation significant wave height (H_s) for a range of wave peak periods (T_p) are

investigated in combination with a 10-year current speed acting in the same direction (Karunakaran and Baarholm, 2013). **Table 4-5** describes the environmental loads applied in the dynamic analysis, more specifically, H_s , T_p , and current.

Table 4-5: Environmental loads description.

Parameters	Value	Units
Wave height, H_s	3	m
Wave peak period, T_p	6-14	s
Current	0.3	m/s
Irregular wave spectrum	JONSWAP	

4.6 Dynamic installation analysis

The dynamic installation analysis was carried out to check the feasibility of the installation method proposed. Only the cable laying procedure is investigated, in other words, after the cable is already connected to the seabed. In this section, the influence of the environmental loads' direction, the T_p , and the water depth during the installation of the HTS cable are discussed.

Figure 4-4 presents the maximum effective tension and maximum bending moments of the HTS cable when subjected to waves and current from several directions i.e. 0° , 45° , 90° , 135° , and 180° . Observing the installation under several environmental load directions, it became clear that the critical direction for cable installation is caused by transversal waves (90° direction). In this regard, **Figure 4-5** illustrates the effect of varying the T_p in the maximum effective tension and bending moments on the HTS cable subjected to transversal waves and current. Although this is the critical load direction, the transversal environmental loads showed to only induce significant stresses to the HTS cable in a limited range of wave peak periods between 8 and 12 s which is near the vessel's natural frequency of vibration in roll.

Figure 4-4: Influence of the environmental loads direction on the maximum effective tension and bending moment of the HTS cable during installation.

Figure 4-5: The effect of varying the wave peak period (T_p) from 6 to 14 s in the maximum effective tension and bending moments on the HTS cable during installation with environmental loads in the 90° direction.

Furthermore, for all load directions, increasing the water depth resulted in higher maximum effective tension and lower maximum bending moment. Figure 4-6 illustrates the influence of water depth in the maximum effective tension and bending moments for environmental loads acting in 180° direction. The dynamic analysis results also showed that the pipe releasing ramp support is responsible for inducing significant bending moments to the HTS cable during installation. Therefore, it is paramount that accurate information about the support’s geometry is used in this type of analysis. In addition, a detailed local analysis should also be performed to evaluate the potential for other failure modes, for example buckling or collapse, that can potentially occur near the support area.

Figure 4-6: Influence of water depth on the maximum effective tension and bending moments of the HTS cable during installation with environmental loads in the 180° direction.

For all cases investigated in this report, the maximum effective tension and maximum bending moments acting on the HTS cable were under the maximum allowable threshold and therefore, satisfied the design criteria for the cable. In addition, because of the low water depths investigated, the tensioner capacity is significantly higher than the maximum top tension. Thus, the installation method proposed is considered suitable for the installation of the HTS cable for H_s under 3 m and water depths up to 100 m. Nonetheless, installation under transversal waves with peak periods near the vessel’s roll natural frequencies should be avoided.

5 Conclusions

In this project, an overview of the current developments in superconducting cables was presented and issues with subsea cables that will affect submarine applications of superconducting cables were discussed and compared. Potential marine applications of superconducting cables in Ireland such as existing and proposed interconnectors and offshore wind farms were reviewed and analysed. A new design methodology for HTS cables to be used in marine applications has been proposed. In addition, detail non-linear finite element models have been developed to calculate the axial and bending stiffnesses of conventional HTS cables, which have not been appropriately reported in published literature. From the conclusion that conventional HTS cables are not suitable for dynamic marine application, a novel structural HTS cable concept was presented that enables such applications of the technology. Finally, the suitability of cable laying and reel-lay vessels to install the HTS cable was investigated and the effects of wave and current directions, wave peak periods and water depth during the installation process were discussed.

Thus, the studies carried out in the SuperMarineOne project concluded:

- (i) Currently, three HTS materials have been demonstrated worldwide for superconducting cable applications i.e. BSCCO, YBCO and MgB_2 . Although there are several deployed and ongoing demonstration SC cable projects worldwide, no clear direction of which SC material is preferred for power cable applications. Due to recent improvements in YBCO-based HTS cables performance, their lower costs in comparison to BSCCO technology, and their intrinsic FCL capability, YBCO seems to have clear advantages over BSCCO wires for HTS cable applications. On the other hand, MgB_2 -based superconducting cable has demonstrated significantly lower costs which are likely to boost the development of MgB_2 -based SC cables in the near future.
- (ii) There are potential marine applications of superconducting technology in Ireland and other countries for adequate infrastructure and technology for offshore transmission and interconnectors. These include possible upgrading of the existing interconnectors such as the Moyle and East-West and introduction into being-developed/proposed interconnectors such as the Greenlink, the Celtic and others. Besides those, there is huge potential for introducing superconducting technology for export cables and collectors in offshore wind farms to exploit the offshore wind potential of 34.8 GW – 39 GW in Ireland and for other significant future potentials of marine renewable energy (wave, tidal and current) in the country. Coupling with other energy sectors by the concepts of offshore wind – hydrogen production hubs being developed by the H-Wind project ⁽¹⁾ is another solution to increase the applications of superconducting technology.
- (iii) It was concluded that the free-hanging configuration is more suitable than the lazy-wave configuration for HTS cable applications at 100 m water depths. Even though the lazy wave configuration minimized the top tension on the cable, the addition of buoyant modulus introduced excessive axial compression that led to cable buckling in both designs. This occurred because the HTS cable is light in comparison to its external diameter and consequently its water displacement.
- (iv) According to the proposed methodology, conventional HTS cable designs used in terrestrial applications are not suitable for dynamic marine applications. In order to allow HTS cables to be

deployed in the marine environment an external armour structure to support the marine loads is required.

- (v) The novel structural concept for HTS cables specific for marine applications satisfied all design criteria in the extreme operation and installation conditions evaluated. This shows that the novel concept could be further investigated and tested for enabling the deployment of HTS technology in a number of marine applications.
- (vi) By comparing cable laying and reel-lay vessels, the latter was considered more suitable to install the HTS cable proposed. The higher MBR while handling the HTS cable and the controllable releasing top angle during installation minimize the stresses induced to the cable during installation and during cable handling by the reel-lay equipment. However, some cable laying vessels may be able to install the HTS cable even though inducing more bending moments than reel-lay vessels due to their equipment onboard. This is important because having two different types of vessels available to be used for installation can be an advantage.
- (vii) From an installation perspective, the critical environmental load direction for cable installation is caused by transversal waves (90° direction). However, this environmental load direction showed to only induce significant stresses to the HTS cable in a limited range of wave peak periods near the vessel's natural frequency of vibration in roll. The results also showed that the pipe releasing ramp support is responsible for inducing significant bending moments to the HTS cable during installation. Therefore, it is paramount that accurate information about the support's geometry is used in this type of analysis. In addition, a detailed local analysis should also be performed to evaluate the potential for other failure modes that can potentially occur near the support area, for example buckling or collapse.

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